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Vanishing mask refinement in semi-supervised video object segmentation

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents Video Object Segmentation Enhanced with Segment Anything Model (VOS-E-SAM), a multi-stage architecture for Semi-supervised Video Object Segmentation (SVOS) using the foundational Segment Anything Model (SAM) architecture, aimed at addressing the challenges of mask degradation over time in long video sequences. Our architectural approach enhances the object masks produced by the XMem model by incorporating SAM. This integration uses various input combinations and low-level computer vision techniques to generate point prompts, in order to improve mask continuity and accuracy throughout the entire video cycle. The main challenge addressed is the fading or vanishing of object masks in long video sequences due to problems such as changes in object appearance, occlusions, camera movements, and approach changes. Both the baseline architecture and the newer high-quality version are tested, addressing the primary challenge of object mask fading or vanishing in long video sequences due to changes in object appearance, occlusions, camera movements, and variations in approach. Through rigorous experimentation with different prompt configurations, we identified an outstanding configuration of SAM inputs to improve mask refinement. Evaluations on benchmark long video datasets, such as LongDataset and LVOS, show that our approach significantly improves mask quality in single-object extended video sequences proven by percentage increments on jaccard index (J) and contour accuracy (F) based metrics (mean, recall and decay). Our results show remarkable improvements in mask persistence and accuracy, which sets a new standard for the integration of foundational models in video segmentation and lays the foundation for future research in this field. [Github.VOS-E-SAM](https://github.com/VOS-E-SAM)

1. Introduction

Video Object Segmentation (VOS) represents an increasingly growing focus within the realm of computer vision. Such segmentation methods are rooted in the overarching concept of either general object detection or the identification of preeminent entities within video streams. VOS techniques are used in various applications such as video surveillance [1,2], activity recognition [3], object tracking [4], autonomous vehicle navigation [5–7], and robotics [8], among others extensively studied in review papers [9,10]. With the advent of advances in parallel computing hardware and the development of contemporary artificial intelligence models, the results achieved evoke astonishment among a multitude of observers [11–13]. Notwithstanding that these results enable the integration of such models into everyday tools with a broad spectrum of applications, enduring challenges still need resolution before a victory in this endeavor. Videos of extended duration,

which encompass multiple objects, changes in perspective, substantial deformations, and require real-time segmentation capabilities or occlusion handling, continue to pose a formidable challenge to even the most sophisticated models. This research is centered on the field of Semi-Supervised Video Object Segmentation (SVOS), where it commences by initially identifying the objects to be segmented. Currently, there are various architectural approaches for SVOS. According to [14] these models can be categorized into Online Fine-Tuning-Based Methods, Propagation-Based Methods, Graph Optimization-Based Methods, Optical Flow-Based Methods, Long-Term Temporal Propagation-Based Methods, and Matching-Based Methods.

- **Online Fine-Tuning-Based Methods** [15–17] are characterized by their ability to adapt pre-trained segmentation networks to the specific objects in a given video through fine-tuning on the

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first annotated frame. The foundational work in this area is One-Shot Video Object Segmentation (OSVOS) [15], which fine-tunes a general object segmentation model on the first frame and applies it to segment the rest of the video. While this approach improves object-specific accuracy, it is computationally intensive due to the need for fine-tuning during inference. Building on OSVOS, OnAVOS (Online Adaptive VOS), [18,19] introduces an adaptive strategy that continuously fine-tunes the model using high-confidence predictions from previous frames, enhancing robustness but further increasing computational demand. To address efficiency concerns, methods like Fast and Robust Target Models for VOS (FRTM) [20] focus on fine-tuning only a subset of model parameters, striking a balance between speed and accuracy by optimizing only the parts of the model most critical for segmentation, thus making real-time applications more feasible.

- **Propagation-Based Methods** [21–23] rely on the assumption that the target objects move smoothly through the consecutive frames in video, using masks from previous frames to guide the segmentation of subsequent frames. MaskTrack [24] is a seminal approach in this category, utilizing the previous frame’s mask to predict the current frame’s mask. This method is straightforward but can falter when objects undergo rapid movements or occlusions, leading to drift in the segmentation. DyeNet [25] improves upon this by incorporating bidirectional mask propagation, where masks are propagated both forward and backward through the video sequence, which helps in managing complex motions and temporary occlusions by using the most accurate mask as a reference, regardless of its position in the sequence.
- **Graph Optimization-Based Methods** take a more global approach to video segmentation by organizing multiple frames into a graph structure to establish extensive temporal correspondences across the video. These methods differ from others by focusing on global optimization rather than frame-by-frame propagation. SCO-VOS (Sequential Clique Optimization for VOS) [26] is a key method that uses a graph where nodes represent object masks across frames, optimizing the segmentation by selecting the most consistent track through this graph. This approach is robust, especially for videos with long sequences or frequent occlusions, but it comes with high computational costs due to the complexity of the graph optimization process. On the other hand, AGNN (Attentive Graph Neural Network) [27] focuses on propagating information across frames by treating each frame as a node in a fully connected graph, enabling the model to capture high-level dependencies and ensuring robustness against complex scene changes.
- **Optical Flow-Based Methods** exploit the motion patterns between consecutive frames to enhance segmentation. These methods assume that different objects have distinct motion patterns, which can be captured by optical flow techniques. MP-Net (Motion Pattern Network) [28] integrates optical flow into the segmentation process to distinguish between moving objects and background, making it particularly effective in dynamic scenes. However, the quality of the optical flow can be affected by challenges such as camera shake or complex backgrounds, leading to potential inaccuracies. CINM (CNN In MRF), [29] addresses some of these issues by using optical flow as a constraint within a Markov Random Field (MRF) framework, refining segmentation masks through this additional temporal information, which improves performance in handling fast-moving objects or complex motion scenarios. The ALBA work [30] is a decoupled multistage video segmentation architecture using reinforcement learning for the clustering of moving entities identified by optical flow. Although it is an unsupervised system that segments all moving instances, the use of optical flow and reinforcement learning allows us to categorize it in this group.

- **Long-Term Temporal Propagation-Based Methods** aim to overcome the limitations of short-term dependencies by capturing long-term temporal relationships across video sequences. These methods often use recurrent neural networks (RNNs) or transformers to accumulate information over a longer period, allowing the model to adapt to changes in object appearance, scale, or background over time. S2S (Sequence-to-Sequence) [31] employs a simple but effective ConvLSTM model to propagate features across frames, capturing long-term dependencies that help in maintaining consistency even in videos with dynamic content. PDB (Pyramid Dilated Bidirectional ConvLSTM) [32] enhances this by integrating multi-scale feature extraction and bidirectional propagation, which improves the model’s ability to handle sequences with varying object sizes and complex motions. In more recent work, SSTVOS (Sparse Spatiotemporal Transformers for VOS) [33] leverages transformers to model long-range dependencies across frames, enabling more accurate segmentation by capturing global context, although at the cost of increased computational resources. XMem [34] and its extended version XMem++ [35] use multiple memory stores to capture different temporal contexts of a video while strictly limiting GPU memory usage. It does this by using the Atkinson–Shiffrin memory model, which includes multiple memory stores with independent but deeply interconnected properties: a rapidly updating sensory memory, a high-resolution working memory, and a compact and therefore persistent long-term memory.
- **Matching-Based Methods** [36,37], establish correspondences between features from different frames to maintain segmentation consistency. These methods are particularly powerful in scenarios where maintaining pixel-level or region-level consistency is crucial across a video sequence. STM (Space-Time Memory Networks) [38] exemplifies pixel-level matching by storing key-value pairs from previous frames in a memory network, which are then matched with features in the current frame to guide segmentation. This approach is robust in handling long videos with complex scenes due to its ability to adapt to changes in object appearance and position. SiamMask [39,40] focuses on region-level matching, combining object tracking with segmentation by matching regions of interest (ROI) across frames, which balances efficiency and accuracy, making it suitable for real-time applications. AOT (Associating Objects with Transformers) [41] represents the cutting-edge in this area, using transformers to establish detailed correspondences across multiple objects in a scene, providing high-precision segmentation even in challenging scenarios with overlapping objects or complex interactions. AMN (Adaptive Memory Network) [42] introduces an innovative approach that adaptively extracts object features by focusing on object areas while filtering out background noise, significantly enhancing segmentation speed and precision in long-term videos.

Despite the promising results obtained by all these architectural frameworks, one of the main challenges facing researchers is the accumulation of errors over the time of the mask propagation video. For example, over the course of a video, objects undergo transformations in their appearance, experience occlusions, encounter camera movements, or undergo perspective changes. Associating the initial information with subsequent frames requires successive propagation of segmentation errors. Furthermore, these models must be trained to perform object segmentation in a generalized way, even though the different shapes and movements of different objects pose a significant challenge. We call this effect of time-propagated segmentation errors “mask vanishing”.

In the field of image segmentation, the Segment Anything Model (SAM) [43] is a groundbreaking foundation model for object segmentation. Unlike specialized models, SAM and its high quality version HQ-SAM [44] can handle a wide range of tasks, achieving near-state-of-the-art results in edge detection, instance segmentation, text-to-mask

conversion, and more, without specific training. Its success can be attributed to three key factors:

- Firstly, SAM was designed and trained in a versatile task called a “promptable segmentation mask”, which allows it to adapt to different tasks by modifying the prompts. Accepts both images and input, specifies the target for segmentation, even in ambiguous cases, and provides reasonable masks.
- Secondly, SAM supports flexible prompts, consisting of multiple interconnected inputs, and responds in real-time, allowing interactive use. Its architecture includes two encoders (for prompts and images) and a “Lightweight mask” decoder to predict segmentation masks.
- Lastly, a SAM-based data engine was developed because of the need for a substantial training dataset that was not readily available. This data engine has generated a public dataset with one billion masks from eleven million images, facilitating further research and model improvement through new training and validation data.

Despite the benefits, using SAM directly for video segmentation does not produce the best results, as it does not take into account the temporal consistency between frames. Therefore, the direct application of SAM to videos does not yield satisfactory results due to its lack of temporal correspondence.

Throughout this paper, we describe a new SVOS model called VOS-E-SAM (Video Object Segmentation Enhanced with Segment Anything Model) for reducing mask vanishing throughout a video segmentation, employing the memory potential of XMem and the powerful performance of SAM and HQ-SAM in image segmentation. The main contribution of this work consists of the proposed multistage architecture, subject to a set of possible configurations for mask refinement. These configurations are based on low-level computer vision techniques that act as an input prompt to the refinement system. The results confirm the significant improvement achieved by the new VOS-E-SAM meta-model compared to the baseline systems, in particular for long video datasets. [Github.VOS-E-SAM](#)

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the work related to SVOS. Section 3 presents the proposed VOS-E-SAM methodology, describing key aspects of its replication. Section 4 describes the experimentation process for system configuration and model validation. For this, Section 4 includes a description of the datasets used, quality metrics, results, and discussions on each of the evaluated datasets. Section 5 presents an ablation study to evaluate the impact of different input configurations on the performance of the proposed architecture. The limitations of the work are included together with the future work in Section 6. Finally, the conclusions of the work are shown in Section 7.

2. Related works

The work titled “Space Time Memory Networks” (STM) [36] represents the pioneering SVOS model that adapted “Space Time” networks, initially used in Natural Language Processing (NLP), to the domain of video segmentation. These architectural frameworks establish a memory structure with which the models interact by reading or writing to achieve their objectives. The STM model propagates segmentation masks by extracting or generating information from stored memory frames, from the initial frame to frame $t-1$, to segment frame t . For each frame, an encoder generates a key and a value, which are representative vectors that allow the search and recovery of information. The STM network is based on an encoder–decoder paradigm, where encoders derive low-dimensional representations of images and masks, and the decoder transforms these data into a mask format consistent with the input. Key–value pairs are crucial in determining the relevance of stored information in memory to segment new frames. The query encoder’s value, combined with the value extracted from memory, generates the

output mask. During training, the encoders are conditioned to generate a “Key” value for robust visual information encoding, while the “Value” values develop joint representations encompassing masks and images for the memory encoder and detailed scene information for the query encoder. The model undergoes a two-step training process: pre-training on static image datasets augmented through affine transformations, followed by further refinement using training datasets.

Building on the STM framework, the study titled “Rethinking Space Time Memory Networks with Improved Memory Coverage for Efficient Video Object Segmentation” (STCN) [45] introduces enhancements by simplifying the architecture and optimizing the read operation. The key innovation is the fusion of the “Key” vector acquisition process from both the “Memory Encoder” and the “Query Encoder” into a single encoder, eliminating the need for a memory encoder to store segmented frames. Researchers argue that the information extractable from an image, used to gauge resemblance to an unannotated frame, bears limited relevance to object segmentation and complicates the information transfer process.

The latest advancement in this line of research is presented in “XMem: Long-Term Video Object Segmentation with an Atkinson–Shiffrin Memory Model” [37]. This model, developed to enhance the processing of extended-duration videos, exceeds existing state-of-the-art performance. XMem’s key innovation is the integration of a novel memory model based on the Atkinson–Shiffrin Memory Model [46], which deviates from the conventional single-information-storage approach. This addition addresses the challenges of excessive memory utilization and declining segmentation accuracy in lengthy videos, common issues in the STM and STCN models. The Atkinson–Shiffrin Memory Model outlines memory as a sequential flow of information across sensory memory, short-term memory, and long-term memory, which XMem leverages to manage memory resources and maintain high segmentation accuracy over long video sequences, making it the leading model in state-of-the-art SVOS and the baseline for evaluating enhancements in the VOS-E-SAM meta-model.

Hybrid models such as the “Track Anything Model” (TAM) [47] and the “Segment And Track Anything Model” (SAM-Track) [48] are also relevant to VOS-E-SAM. TAM combines the XMem model with SAM, enabling video segmentation through a user-friendly interface. Users can annotate videos with SAM and propagate masks with XMem, iteratively refining the segmentation by adjusting masks with SAM. SAM-Track, which combine SAM with AOT and Grounding-DINO, offers a pipeline that supports interactive and automated segmentation and tracking of objects throughout a video, enhancing the overall segmentation process in dynamic and complex environments; however, SAM interaction only occurs at system initialization.

In the VOS-E-SAM model, the refinement of XMem incorporates the Segment Anything Model (SAM) [43] to prevent mask vanishing. SAM consolidates multiple tasks within a single model, eliminating the need for numerous task-specific models. Recently, the “Segment Anything in High Quality” (HQ-SAM) model [49] has been introduced, building on SAM’s architecture to enhance its performance, particularly in “Zero-Shot” tasks and complex object segmentation. This optimization is achieved with minimal parameter increases and brief training, leading to significant improvements in image segmentation metrics. VOS-E-SAM aims to integrate these advances into its framework to ensure robust and accurate segmentation in challenging video sequences.

3. Video object segmentation enhanced with SAM: VOS-E-SAM

The proposal of this work combines the potential of XMem and SAM for SVOS, with the aim of reducing the degradation of the masks along the videos. For this purpose, the [Github.VOS-E-SAM](#) model is proposed, which consists of a multi-step process described below.

Given the frame $f_{t=0} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times H_0 \times W_0}$ and masks $M_{t=0,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times W_0}$ of the j th target objects in the first frame (left of Fig. 1), XMem tracks the j th objects and generates the corresponding j -masks for the following query

Fig. 1. VOS-E-SAM architecture.

Fig. 2. Example transformation into Centroid per Contour.

frames f_t . The first frame initializes the different XMem memories as indicated by its authors [34]. For each subsequent query frame f_t , XMem reads out the short-term sensory memory $h_{t-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{C^H \times H \times W}$ and the features $F \in \mathbb{R}^{C^H \times H \times W}$ representing the information stored in the long-term and working memories. The information from the readout is used to generate the output masks $M_{t,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_t \times W_t}$ by the XMem decoder. This decoder concatenates the hidden representation h_{t-1} and the features F .

Then, the feature map computed during the 4 steps is projected onto a single-channel logit through a 3×3 convolution and bilinearly expanded to the resolution of the input image $H \times W$ following the XMem steps [34]. The masks $M_{t,j}$ of the query frame f_t at this t -time, are subjected to refinement using SAM. For this purpose, the query frame is introduced in the SAM image encoder and in the prompt encoder a prompt $\mathcal{P} \in \{\text{key points, bounding boxes, mask, and combinations}\}$ object of study for this work.

This approach to using foundational models such as SAM to refine the output mask of video segmentation methods is completely innovative and opens up a new avenue of research to improve the results of these models. Although TAM and SAM-Track utilize the said model for initialization in the first mask and the use of semi-supervised models, this work refines each of the output masks from XMem by transforming and adapting them to the input of the SAM model.

Using foundational models as refinement masks helps the model achieve better accuracy in object segmentation and provides improved temporal consistency as SAM is trained on a diverse dataset including objects with occlusions and ambiguous boundaries, helping reduce inaccuracies on frame-to-frame mask propagation. Unlike this, the zero-shot capability named SAM's paper allows the refining of segmentation masks on objects and contexts that the model was not specifically trained on, further enhancing its performance in varied and unseen scenarios.

The SAM model is multi-modal in nature because the inputs for the segmentation of objects in images allow for different formats masks, points, boxes, and text called prompt \mathcal{P} . In the VOS-E-SAM architecture, points, bounding boxes, masks, and combinations between them are used as input prompt for the SAM base model.

The translation of XMem model output to SAM model input can be executed in various ways, allowing multiple combinations to identify the best approach. From the XMem model, we acquire, for each object, the pixel-wise probability of membership and the logits of the same output. The first output of the model is utilized to compute various forms of points and the bounding boxes of the objects, while the logits are transformed and employed as input masks for the SAM model. It is important to recall that the image input is not processed at any time, so it is delegated to XMem to propagate the initial mask provided by the user of the system.

The computation of the bounding box is straightforward. The maximum and minimum values of the non-zero elements within each binary mask output by XMem on both image axes yield the exact values anticipated by SAM.

In contrast, determining the characteristic object points to be used as prompts in the SAM model is a more intricate process. Selecting the most suitable points that define an object for optimizing the SAM output is a complex procedure aimed at enhancing its performance. Although the possibilities are virtually limitless, considering the wide array of objects and their varied shapes and positions in videos, several methods and low-level computer vision algorithms have been selected and implemented to conduct extensive testing and assess the performance of each approach.

The methods used to calculate key points in an image or mask are as follows.

- **Centroid per Contour:** The centroid, or geometric center, of a shape has been computed using the "Moments" function from the OpenCV library. This function calculates various spatial and central moments of a binary shape. Subsequently, the spatial moments M_{00} , M_{01} , and M_{10} are used to calculate the centroid of shape with (1).

$$Centroid(x, y) = \left(\frac{M_{10}}{M_{00}}, \frac{M_{01}}{M_{00}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Trough adjusted to the nearest point within the mask when it falls outside the mask itself, for example for concave shapes. To calculate that particular point all Euclidean distances from the centroid to each mask point have been calculated the minimum distance

Fig. 3. Example transformation into Contour Polyline.

Fig. 4. Example transformation into Contour Polyline Skeleton Key Points.

point is selected as the new centroid. This approach is similarly applied in other contexts such as the work of Shanmugam, M. et al. [50]. Given that an object may consist of more than one contour, the centroid of each contour has been computed (see Fig. 2).

- **Contour Polyline:** A contour consists of numerous points, and the larger the object in relation to the dimensions of the video, the more points the algorithm calculates (see Fig. 3).
- **Skeleton Key Points:** The low-level Skeleton algorithm converts a figure generated by a binary mask into its topological representation with a width of 1 pixel. This is achieved by successive erosion of the contour of the figure until the desired result is achieved [51]. This skeleton, like the contour, calculates too many points, which hinders the correct usage of SAM. Therefore, algorithms have been implemented to extract key points from this global set of points. The end points and junction points of the figure have been identified. Additionally, the midpoints of each pair of directly connected end and junction points have been determined. This has resulted in the calculation of the midpoints of the branches generated by these points (see Fig. 4).

All these methods for calculating key points can be combined and mixed in various ways to obtain the maximum number of points that define and improve the SAM model's output.

The points received by the SAM model can be of two types. The points can be positive or negative. Positive points are those with which the user indicates that the selected pixel is part of the object they want to segment, while negative points are those in the image that the user indicates belong to objects different from the object they want to segment. With this idea in mind, and considering that we have points belonging to objects as well as the space occupied by each object calculated as a “bounding box”, it is possible to determine which points of an object other than the one to be segmented are within the bounding box of the object to be segmented. As seen in Fig. 5, with this approach we can more accurately specify the location of the object we want to segment.

The aforementioned inputs can be combined without limitation, providing a broad spectrum of possibilities for SAM users to achieve their desired results.

4. Results and discussion

In order to identify the best prompt configuration for mask refinement with SAM, a massive experimentation with different configurations is proposed. The different configurations of the proposal are compared with the base XMem system over four datasets, using video and image segmentation quality metrics to consider both the individual (image) segmentation and the aggregated temporal set of videos.

This section will outline the results of the various tests conducted on the newly proposed architecture. Initially, an overview of the datasets used in these tests is presented. Subsequently, the metrics used to assess the performance of this novel approach are detailed. Lastly, the results achieved are expounded and analyzed.

VOS-E-SAM has been tested on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 with checkpoints for XMem, SAM and HQ-SAM. The results of the different configurations for each of the evaluation datasets are compared with the base XMem system, using the set of quality metrics to discuss the results.

4.1. Datasets

A selection of established datasets has been made, specifically chosen to comprehensively evaluate the newly proposed architecture. These datasets encompass:

- **DAVIS.** The “Densely Annotated Video Segmentation” dataset is a diverse collection of short-duration videos featuring files in various resolutions. It presents challenges such as appearance changes and occasional occlusions. The dataset includes dense annotations for each of its frames. Presently, this dataset is available in two distinct versions: DAVIS 2016 [52] and DAVIS 2017 [53]. The 2016 version comprises 50 videos, while the 2017 version comprises up to 150 videos. The primary disparity between the two versions lies in the inclusion of multi-object scenarios in DAVIS2017. Although the 2017 dataset features videos with single and multi-objects, it serves as a comprehensive benchmark to evaluate the challenges faced by video segmentation models. In

Fig. 5. Positive and negative points SAM.

both cases, training sets have been used for model architecture decisions, while a validation set has been reserved for testing.

- The “Long-Time Video Dataset” introduced by the researchers along with their model [54], was designed to assess the practical limitations of video segmentation models. This dataset consists of only three exceptionally long videos, spanning 1,416, 3,589, and 2,406 frames. Importantly, object segmentation information is available only for a total of 21 frames within these videos. What distinguishes this dataset is the discontinuous nature of the camera’s operation throughout the video sequences, involving frequent cuts and changes in perspective while tracking objects. These camera transitions introduce additional complexities, compelling models to develop a deeper comprehension of objects due to potential abrupt changes in object proximity or angle. Furthermore, the dataset encompasses scenarios with object disappearances and occlusions. Training set has been used for model decisions and validation set for testing performance
- The “Long-term Video Object Segmentation” (LVOS) [55] benchmark represents a pioneering dataset specifically designed for the development and evaluation of VOS models capable of handling realistic long-duration video content. This dataset is a significant departure from existing benchmarks that predominantly feature short clips lasting only a few seconds, where objects of interest are almost always visible. LVOS stands out by offering 220 videos that cumulatively span 421 min, with an average length of approximately 1.59 min (or 574 frames at 6 frames per second) per video. This makes each LVOS video about 20 times longer than those found in conventional VOS datasets, providing a much more representative sample of real-world applications.

4.2. Metrics

The evaluation metrics used to measure the performance of the VOS-E-SAM architecture originate from the convergence of two distinct research domains incorporated within the model. On the one hand, we have video metrics that are tasked with evaluating the robustness of segmentation and its consistency throughout the video sequence. Meanwhile, the image metrics focus on the examination of individual frames in isolation, emphasizing variations in results with respect to object size.

4.2.1. Video object segmentation

In the realm of SVOS, three primary metrics have been used in recent years to elucidate and evaluate the results, as well as to facilitate comparisons of diverse models across benchmark datasets. These metrics include:

- The Jaccard index \mathcal{J} , (2), also known as Intersection over Union (IoU), assesses the accuracy of mask volume and is calculated by taking the ratio of the intersection of the generated mask P and

the ground truth mask G over their union, as implied by its name.

$$\mathcal{J}(G, P) = \frac{G \cap P}{G \cup P} \quad (2)$$

- Contour Accuracy \mathcal{F} assesses the F_1 score based on the classification of points within the contour of the mask. To compute this final value, the precision and recall for the contours of both masks are calculated using a morphological approach to bipartite graph matching [56]. Its value is derived from (3).

$$\mathcal{F} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (3)$$

These metrics, depending on their aggregation and calculation methods, can be presented in various formats. In the field of video segmentation, each metric is typically calculated on a per-frame basis, and three common calculations are employed. For all three metrics the Jaccard Index is used as reference though Contour Accuracy would be calculated exactly the same:

- Mean: The value is computed for each frame and then averaged per video. Finally, the mean is presented for the entire dataset, with each video’s mean calculated separately. For a specific dataset D with V number of videos, F number of frames in a video, and N number of objects in each frame, we first calculate the Jaccard index of a frame as the mean of all Jaccard values for each object appearing. Then the Jaccard Index of a video is considered the mean of all individual Jaccard Indexes of each frame. Finally, the mean of all the Jaccard Index video values is used to compute the Jaccard Index of a specific dataset. (4)

$$\text{Mean } \mathcal{J}_d = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^V \left(\frac{1}{F} \sum_{j=1}^F \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \mathcal{J}(G_{i,j,k}, P_{i,j,k}) \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

- Decay: Decay refers to how the mask error propagates throughout the video segmentation process. The closest approximation to the true object segmentation occurs with the initial mask. Therefore, understanding how each metric changes from the first frame to the last frame provides valuable insights into how the error accumulates frame by frame. The model propagates information frame by frame, but it also accumulates errors, which depend on the previously calculated masks and the difficulty of segmenting new frames. To calculate the decay, the difference between the metric in the first 25% of the frames and the final 25% of the frames is computed. Subsequently, the average of all videos is calculated to determine the decay of that specific metric across the entire dataset. Having Q_1 and Q_4 as the subsets of the first 25% of frames and the last 25% of frames respectively, the Decay Jaccard Index of a video is computed as the difference between the mean of each group. Its values is derived form (5)

$$\text{Decay } \mathcal{J}_d = \text{Mean } \mathcal{J}(Q_4) - \text{Mean } \mathcal{J}(Q_1) \quad (5)$$

- Recall: This is a binary metric that serves as a flag, indicating whether a certain value exceeds a predefined threshold. For each frame and object, it is determined whether the metric exceeds this threshold and, for each video, the percentage of frames that exceed the threshold is calculated. Ultimately, all videos are averaged to provide the final result. Jaccard Index Decay at 50% for a specific dataset is derived from (6)

$$Recall \mathcal{J}_d = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^V \left(\frac{1}{F} \sum_{j=1}^F \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \mathcal{J}(G_{i,j,k}, P_{i,j,k}) \right) > 0.5 \right) \quad (6)$$

In addition, the average value of \mathcal{J} and \mathcal{F} is usually expressed as $\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$ is usually used to evaluate the overall performance of a segmentation model.

4.2.2. Image segmentation

In this section, image segmentation evaluation metrics are introduced, since the proposed architecture seeks to individually refine each mask propagated by XMem along the video to reduce mask vanishing. To evaluate this innovation, a global quality metric analysis of the image segmentation is required.

In the field, the most commonly used metric is Average Precision (AP). This metric is computed by calculating the area under the curve (AUC) of the Precision–Recall curve. Note that this metric is typically calculated for each class of objects present in the dataset. Since it is not a metric specific to video segmentation, and the datasets used may not consistently encompass all object classes, the value is calculated on a per-video basis. Once the values for individual videos are determined, the final metric is calculated as the average of these values in all videos.

The calculation of ‘Average Precision’ in the COCO paper [57], a standard in this field, is performed in six different ways, resulting in six final metrics for each test. The first three metrics vary according to the IoU threshold, while the last three depend on the size of the object to be segmented.

The most crucial metric, often referred to as the ‘Primary Challenge Metric’ by COCO researchers, employs ten different thresholds for the metric calculation. The final result AP is derived from the arithmetic mean of these ten thresholds. These thresholds are initially set from 0.5 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05. The other two metrics are based on a single threshold, 0.5 for the first and 0.75 for the second. In the original paper, these three metrics were calculated per type of object and then averaged overall. In the context of this study and to ensure a consistent calculation of metrics across datasets, calculations have been performed per video, culminating in the overall average.

The metric per object type is calculated in the same way as the previous one, in the format AP [.50, .05, .95] for each video, but separating the objects according to their area into three groups. Group ‘small’ when the area is less than or equal to 32^2 , ‘medium’ when it is between 32^2 and 96^2 , and ‘large’ when it is greater than 96^2 . The area was calculated on the basis of the mask of each object, not the bounding box that delimits it.

Once the values have been calculated for each video in each set, the overall mean is calculated, as in the case of general AP . It is important to note that since these are videos, the size of the objects within them may vary as the objects move towards and away from the camera, as well as encountering obstacles. Each object in each frame of each video has been treated as a separate object, and its group membership has been calculated on the basis of the size of its mask.

The selected metrics cover the different problems that segmentation models can present. Table 1 compiles all the selected metrics and explains the problem each of them evaluates.

Table 1
Summary table of chosen video and image metrics.

Type	Metric	Id	Evaluation
Video	Jaccard Distance Mean	\mathcal{J}	Output and reality intersection error
	Jaccard Distance Recall	\mathcal{J}_{Recall}	Percentage of frames whose IoU value is greater than 50%
	Jaccard Distance Decay	\mathcal{J}_{Decay}	Drop in IoU value of last frames vs. first frames
	Boundary Accuracy Mean	\mathcal{F}	Error in the accuracy of the contrast between output and reality
	Boundary Accuracy Recall	\mathcal{F}_{Recall}	Percentage of frames whose boundary accuracy value is greater than 50%
	Boundary Accuracy Decay	\mathcal{F}_{Decay}	Drop in boundary accuracy value of last frames vs. first frames
	Jaccard and Boundary Mean	$\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$	Overall performance of the model. Average of both values
Image	Average Precision	AP	Precision of predictions for different tolerance levels in the IoU metric
	Average Precision [.50]	$AP_{@0.5}$	Prediction precision for a single tolerance level 50% in the IoU metric
	Average Precision [.75]	$AP_{@0.75}$	Prediction precision for a single tolerance level of 75% on the IoU metric
	Average Precision Small	AP_s	Precision at different tolerance levels for small objects
	Average Precision Medium	AP_m	Precision at different tolerance levels for medium objects
	Average Precision Large	AP_l	Precision at different tolerance levels for large objects

4.3. VOS-E-SAM architecture parameters

Different configurations of the VOS-E-SAM architecture have been constructed. These variants depend on whether various inputs from the SAM model were utilized and whether the initial SAM model or the HQ-SAM model was employed. HQ-SAM has been introduced into the architecture as its authors demonstrate improved performance in overall accuracy and preservation of detail.

The inputs included ‘Bounding Boxes’ (B), positive points (P), negative points (N), and masks (M), which were combined in various ways. Three distinct methods were used for point transformation: Contour Centroid (C), Contour Polyline plus Centroid (CP), Polyline Centroid, and Skeleton Key Points (CPS). Table 2 shows all the combinations used for each dataset.

The increase in quantity and addition of complex inputs for SAM was done iteratively using the training sets of each presented dataset to check whether each transformation decision led to better results overall in all data sets. Starting only with a representative point, complexity progressively increased as certain complex movement and occlusion scenarios appeared in the first results. This iterative process of implementing transformation and checking performance in training sets led to the development of different forms of point selection, adding both bounding boxes and masks, and using other object bounding boxes to compute negative points to improve contour definition.

When identifying the models in the tables, the text “SAM” or “HQ” will precede the test ID, indicating refinement with the original model or the model “High Quality”, respectively. For datasets with a single object per video, such as DAVIS 2016 or LongDataset, models that use both positive and negative points will be denoted with the identifier “P(N)”. This indicates that, given the unique objects per frame in these datasets, there will never be a negative one.

Table 2
Model list for testing.

ID	Mask	B. Box	Pos. P.	Neg. P.	Points
XMem	X	X	X	X	-
B	X	✓	X	X	-
P C	X	X	✓	X	Contour Centroid
P CP	X	X	✓	X	Contour & Polyline
P CPS	X	X	✓	X	Cont. Poly. & Skeleton
BP C	X	✓	✓	X	Contour Centroid
BP CP	X	✓	✓	X	Contour & Polyline
BP CPS	X	✓	✓	X	Cont. Poly. & Skeleton
BPN C	X	✓	✓	✓	Contour Centroid
BPN CP	X	✓	✓	✓	Contour & Polyline
BPN CPS	X	✓	✓	✓	Cont. Poly. & Skeleton
MB	✓	✓	X	X	-
MP C	✓	X	✓	X	Contour Centroid
MP CP	✓	X	✓	X	Contour & Polyline
MP CPS	✓	X	✓	X	Cont. Poly. & Skeleton
MBP C	✓	✓	✓	X	Contour Centroid
MBP CP	✓	✓	✓	X	Contour & Polyline
MBP CPS	✓	✓	✓	X	Cont. Poly. & Skeleton
MBPN C	✓	✓	✓	✓	Contour Centroid
MBPN CP	✓	✓	✓	✓	Contour & Polyline
MBPN CPS	✓	✓	✓	✓	Cont. Poly. & Skeleton

4.4. DAVIS

Table 3 presents a summary of the most significant image and video metrics achieved by the top ten models, organized by the average ‘Jaccard’ and ‘F-Score’ values of these metrics across each dataset. It is evident that the superior model for both datasets was HQ MBPN CP, which achieved superior results in ‘Average Precision’ (AP) for both datasets, albeit with slightly lower performance in video metrics. Most of architecture top performers show a combination of the most complex inputs transformations including masks, bounding boxes, positive points, and negative points (only for DAVIS2017) computed with a mixture of the three point transformation techniques.

Fig. 6 shows improvements over the XMem (our baseline) results. In the first image, the refinement managed to fully recover the mask of the motorcycle. In the second image, fine details such as the lower body of the driver have been differentiated from the vehicle. In the third image, the lower part of the box has completed the mask without losing the detail of the person’s mask holding it. Finally, in the last image, the VOSE refinement has managed to differentiate the motorcycle’s glass, separating it from the rear vehicle glass, as well as improve the mask of the rider in the hip area.

4.5. LongDataset

Table 4 displays the results of the twelve main models evaluated in LongDataset using video metrics. The table highlights that the original XMem model ranks tenth within this group, leading only in the J_{Recall} metric, as do almost all models placed above it. The results of this particular dataset reveal significant advantages in employing refinement techniques to derive object masks for long videos. The best-performing model achieves an increase 2.02% in the $J&F$ metric, with 2.36% originating from the Jaccard metric and 1.68% from the F-Score metric. Furthermore, the decay values for both metrics are lower than those of the base model. It is essential to note that the negative decay values associated with the metrics indicate that the masks obtained for the final frames are closer to reality than those acquired at the beginning. This phenomenon is due to the dataset not being entirely annotated, with annotations distributed over 20 frames throughout the video.

Table 5 presents the results of the image metrics obtained on LongDataset. It demonstrates that ten out of the eleven tested models outperform XMem across the board. XMem only matches the results in $AP_{@0.5}$ but it significantly lags behind in many of the ‘Average

Precision’ metrics. The absolute differences between the best model, HQ MP CP, and XMem are as follows: 8.89% in AP , 13.95% in $AP_{@0.75}$, 6.13% in AP_m , and 6.46% in AP_l . The AP_s metric is not reported because no mask in this dataset meets the small object constraint specified by COCO. In addition, Table 5 and Table 6 show how the proposed architecture at least five or more input combinations for SAM/HQ-SAM outperforms XMem in almost all metrics. These results confirm the performance improvement of the proposed architecture for large video datasets.

All videos, on average, demonstrate improved results in the refined VOS-E-SAM version compared to the base version (XMem). Fig. 7 illustrates this improvement. In both the first and second images, it is observable that the refined masks of the person to be segmented has recovered part of the complete object. The improvement in the second image is more subtle; the lower part of the mouse, which is partially occluded by the railing, is recovered after refinement.

4.6. LVOS

The best results obtained for both LongDataset and Davis have been executed on the LVOS dataset to confirm their performance improvement. No architecture modifications have been made based on performance on any of the sets of this dataset and test set has been used for testing. It is important to note that the results obtained include only objects with masks at the beginning of the video, discarding those objects added in frames later on. Only the six best previous architecture combinations based on the results in the previous datasets were executed.

It can be observed in Table 6 that the results of all models in most metrics surpass those obtained by the base model. It can be seen that on average the SAM model with mask and point refinement achieves a 1% higher efficiency than the base model. These results confirm that the proposed architecture improves videos of very long duration, such as the LVOS dataset.

Fig. 8 shows with some examples the improved performance of the proposed VOS-E-SAM proposal in some frames of certain videos on LVOS. First and last show the improvement on animals on close pictures, while second and third show the performance improvement on small, far away objects.

4.7. Enhancement

Previous test show the performance of SAM substituting all mask with the output of SAM, but SAM based models forecast the expected IoU (Jaccard Index) metric of the three output masks it generates; this allows the model to be used in single output by ordering the expected values and picking the best performance mask. This same value can be used to determine whether a refined mask might outperform the base segmented mask by XMem, substituting the initial segmented mask only if certain threshold is surpassed.

In this sense, several tests have been performed with the best performing models presented in the tables before and are summarized in Tables 7 and 8. These tables show the improvement performance for the best prompt configuration for SAM and HQ-SAM respectively substituting only the frames where the foundational model predicted IoU is higher than a defined threshold value for each segmentation model. The results of the quality metrics presented in the tables for the different datasets evaluated show that our configuration achieves better results on average for both short and long videos.

For the architecture enhanced by SAM model, the combination of inputs of: mask, bounding boxes, positive and negative points calculated with centroid, polyline and skeleton transformations output the best metrics outperforming XMem based model for all metrics in long video datasets (LVOS and LongDataset) whilst maintaining similar performance overall in Davis2016 and Davis2017. For the architecture selected best with HQ-SAM, same input configuration than previous

Table 3
Comparison of results in DAVIS datasets.

Model	DAVIS 2016 val				DAVIS 2017 val				Both	
	$J&F$	J	F	AP	$J&F$	J	F	AP	$J&F$	AP
XMem	91.95	90.67	93.24	83.49	87.8	84.0	91.4	77.81	89.86	80.65
HQ MBPN CP	91.63	90.63	92.62	84.03	86.8	83.8	89.90	79.08	89.22	81.56
HQ MBPN C	91.59	90.8	92.39	83.92	86.7	83.7	89.9	78.99	89.15	81.46
SAM MBPN CPS	91.38	89.99	92.77	82.67	87.2	84.1	90.3	79.7	89.29	81.19
SAM MBPN CP	91.27	90.2	92.33	83.13	87.2	84.1	90.2	78.99	89.24	81.4
HQ MBPN CPS	91.34	90.16	92.51	83.14	86.6	83.4	89.7	78.71	88.97	80.93
SAM MBPN C	89.77	88.73	90.82	80.52	86.9	83.8	90.0	78.36	88.36	79.44
SAM MBP CP	91.27	90.2	92.33	83.13	85.4	82.1	88.7	77.35	88.34	80.24
SAM MBP C	89.77	88.73	90.82	80.52	85.7	82.5	89.0	77.74	87.74	79.13
HQ MP CP	91.68	90.68	92.68	83.99	83.6	80.4	86.8	75.55	87.64	79.77
HQ MBP CP	91.63	90.63	92.62	84.03	83.7	80.04	87.0	75.14	87.67	79.59

Fig. 6. Properly refined frames DAVIS 2017 using the new architecture VOS-E-SAM.

except for skeleton points, refinement results show that the performance on long dataset videos is also better, only reducing in terms of hundredths on J_{Decay} and F_{Decay} while outperforming in terms of tenths in F and J and maintaining both recall metrics in LongDataset. Results on both DAVIS dataset are slightly better meaning this architecture is the best performer of all tested.

The DAVIS2016 dataset is fully composed by single-object videos while DAVIS2017 mixes both single and multi-object scenarios. These presented results on last tables show that there is an improvement in mask accuracy, Jaccard index, on single-objects scenarios while performing just under XMem on boundary accuracy for multi-object

scenes for short videos while performing better on mostly all metrics for the mixture of single-object and long video scenarios presented by LongDataset and LVOS.

5. Ablation study

Ablation studies have been done in order to prove that the selected combination of artifacts used as prompts for SAM enrich the output. Ablation results have been divided into two parts: Prompt Ablation and Point Ablation. The former tests all possible input combinations (prompts) [mask (M), bounding-boxes (B) and points (P & N)] while

Fig. 7. Frames correctly refined by the VOS-E-SAM architecture on LongDataset.

Table 4 LongDataset video metrics top performers comparison.

Model	LongDataset						
	$J\&F$	J	J_{Recall}	J_{Decay}	F	F_{Recall}	F_{Decay}
HQ MP CP	89.35	<u>88.27</u>	98.33	-4.06	90.44	98.33	-0.77
HQ MBP(N) CP	<u>89.28</u>	88.33	98.33	-4.05	<u>90.23</u>	<u>96.67</u>	-0.58
HQ MBP(N) CPS	<u>89.16</u>	<u>88.3</u>	98.33	-3.15	<u>90.02</u>	95.0	0.12
HQ MP CPS	<u>89.12</u>	<u>88.06</u>	98.33	-2.56	<u>90.17</u>	<u>96.67</u>	0.45
SAM MP CP	<u>88.89</u>	<u>87.64</u>	98.33	-5.52	<u>90.14</u>	98.33	-3.06
SAM MBP(N) CPS	<u>88.76</u>	<u>87.7</u>	98.33	-3.92	<u>89.83</u>	95.0	0.51
SAM MP CPS	<u>88.74</u>	<u>87.76</u>	98.33	-4.15	<u>89.72</u>	95.0	-0.04
SAM MBP(N) CP	<u>88.61</u>	<u>87.33</u>	98.33	-4.46	<u>89.89</u>	98.33	-2.04
HQ MBP(N) C	<u>87.36</u>	<u>85.79</u>	<u>96.67</u>	-2.18	<u>88.92</u>	<u>96.67</u>	-0.15
XMem	87.33	85.91	98.33	-0.71	88.76	95.0	0.76
HQ MB	86.04	84.11	93.33	1.19	87.97	93.33	2.51
SAM MBP(N) C	85.75	84.32	98.33	-3.78	87.19	98.33	-0.59

Table 5 LongDataset image metrics best performers comparison.

Model	LongDataset					
	AP	$AP_{@.5}$	$AP_{@.75}$	AP_s	AP_m	AP_l
HQ MP CP	75.25	93.33	<u>85.06</u>	-	58.81	80.49
HQ MBP(N) CP	<u>75.02</u>	93.33	86.02	-	<u>61.13</u>	<u>79.66</u>
HQ MP CPS	<u>74.82</u>	93.33	<u>80.92</u>	-	<u>58.84</u>	<u>79.71</u>
HQ MBP(N) CPS	<u>74.81</u>	93.33	<u>85.0</u>	-	61.25	<u>79.22</u>
SAM MBP(N) CPS	<u>73.7</u>	93.33	<u>85.0</u>	-	<u>57.67</u>	<u>78.95</u>
SAM MP CPS	<u>73.49</u>	93.33	<u>83.06</u>	-	<u>58.39</u>	<u>78.16</u>
SAM MBP(N) CP	<u>72.24</u>	93.33	<u>80.52</u>	-	<u>56.92</u>	<u>78.33</u>
SAM MP CP	<u>72.01</u>	93.33	<u>82.29</u>	-	<u>57.33</u>	<u>77.98</u>
HQ MBP(N) C	<u>69.02</u>	91.58	<u>71.22</u>	-	<u>53.55</u>	<u>74.99</u>
SAM MBP(N) C	<u>66.97</u>	93.33	<u>71.25</u>	-	48.89	72.73
XMem	66.36	93.33	71.11	-	52.86	74.03
HQ B	65.81	90.75	68.05	-	51.74	72.08

Table 6 LongVOS video metrics top performers comparison.

Model	LongVOS						
	$J\&F$	J	J_{Seen}	J_{Unseen}	F	F_{Seen}	F_{Unseen}
SAM MP CP	45.77	42.91	41.73	44.09	48.63	<u>46.15</u>	51.11
HQ MBPN CP	45.57	42.55	41.49	43.62	48.58	<u>46.07</u>	<u>51.10</u>
SAM MBPN CPS	<u>45.57</u>	<u>42.52</u>	<u>41.53</u>	<u>43.51</u>	<u>48.62</u>	46.18	<u>51.06</u>
HQ MP CP	<u>45.61</u>	<u>42.75</u>	<u>41.50</u>	<u>44.00</u>	<u>48.47</u>	45.85	<u>51.08</u>
HQ MBPN CPS	<u>45.59</u>	<u>42.50</u>	<u>41.34</u>	<u>43.67</u>	<u>48.47</u>	45.87	<u>51.07</u>
XMem	44.71	41.47	40.93	42.01	47.95	45.88	50.02
SAM MBPN CP	44.68	<u>41.70</u>	<u>41.27</u>	<u>42.13</u>	47.66	<u>45.94</u>	49.39

maintaining point computation (C+P+S) for those combinations that apply, while the latter maintains a particular combination of inputs and simplifies the computation of points [contour (C), polyline (P) and skeleton (S)]. Two different ablations studies are shown for the top models selected for enhancement in the previous section shown in Tables 7 and 8. Table 9 shows results for the model using XMem and SAM while Table 10 shows results for XMem and HQ-SAM. Both tables use single-object DAVIS2016 and multi-object DAVIS2017 as reference datasets for this study. Results show that adding configuration and complexity to inputs to VOS-E-SAM architecture better overall performance in all metrics. Although deeper conclusions can be extracted from the tables:

- Masks make a huge difference in the refinement of output objects in single and multi-object videos as in both tables and both studies the combinations of inputs that add Masks (M) to input configuration return highest metrics on both dataset.
- The inclusion of Skeleton points (S) in both SAM and HQ-SAM architectures makes no significant difference. Slightly better results are shown by the SAM model and slight worse on HQ-SAM.

Fig. 8. Frames correctly refined by the VOS-E-SAM architecture on LongVOS.

Table 7
Enhanced version of HQ MBPN CP against XMem base model.

HQ-SAM MBPN CP*							
Dataset	$J \& F$	J	J_{Recall}	J_{Decay}	F	F_{Recall}	F_{Decay}
DAVIS2016	92.17 _{+0.22}	91.10 _{+0.43}	97.91 _{+0.0}	3.09 _{-0.56}	93.24 _{+0.0}	96.77 _{+0.74}	3.48 _{+0.0}
DAVIS2017	87.50 _{-0.20}	84.10 _{+0.1}	92.70 _{-0.2}	2.90 _{-0.7}	90.90 _{-0.5}	96.80 _{-0.2}	6.20 _{-0.8}
LongDataset	87.70 _{+0.37}	86.15 _{+0.24}	98.33 _{+0.0}	-0.65 _{+0.06}	89.26 _{+0.50}	95.0 _{+0.0}	0.85 _{+0.09}
LVOS							
Dataset	$J \& F$	J	J_{Seen}	J_{Unseen}	F	F_{Seen}	F_{Unseen}
LVOS	45.00 _{+0.29}	41.81 _{+0.34}	41.11 _{+0.18}	42.51 _{+0.50}	48.19 _{+0.24}	45.97 _{+0.09}	50.42 _{+0.39}

Table 8
Enhanced version of SAM MBPN CPS against XMem base model.

SAM MBPN CPS*							
Dataset	$J \& F$	J	J_{Recall}	J_{Decay}	F	F_{Recall}	F_{Decay}
DAVIS2016	92.15 _{+0.20}	91.09 _{+0.42}	97.91 _{+0.0}	3.23 _{-0.42}	93.20 _{-0.04}	96.51 _{-0.52}	3.46 _{-0.02}
DAVIS2017	87.50 _{-0.20}	84.30 _{+0.3}	92.80 _{-0.1}	2.00 _{-1.6}	90.70 _{-0.7}	96.50 _{-0.5}	5.20 _{-1.8}
LongDataset	87.59 _{+0.23}	86.02 _{+0.11}	98.33 _{+0.0}	-0.78 _{-0.07}	89.15 _{+0.39}	95.0 _{+0.0}	0.91 _{+0.15}
LVOS							
Dataset	$J \& F$	J	J_{Seen}	J_{Unseen}	F	F_{Seen}	F_{Unseen}
LVOS	44.84 _{+0.13}	41.61 _{+0.14}	41.00 _{+0.07}	42.23 _{+0.22}	48.07 _{+0.12}	45.98 _{+0.09}	50.17 _{+0.14}

- The complexity of point importance, just Centroid (C), adding Contour Polyline (P) and adding Skeleton (S) makes a bigger difference for SAM based model and lesser in HQ-SAM as average results vary less from C to CPS in Point study of Table 10 showing that HQ-SAM achieves better results with simpler transformations.

6. Limitations and future work

This work has not sought computational efficiency, so the performance of the system in this regard has not been evaluated. The neural

Table 9
Ablation Study for XMem + SAM MBPN {C + P + S} on DAVIS datasets.

Model	DAVIS 2016 val				DAVIS 2017 val				
	$J&F$	J	F	AP	$J&F$	J	F	AP	
Prompt	XMem + SAM P {C + P + S}	82.46	82.00	82.93	68.84	77.1	74.0	80.1	62.88
	XMem + SAM BP {C + P + S}	81.82	81.33	82.30	67.62	77.3	74.3	80.2	62.58
	XMem + SAM BPN {C + P + S}	81.82	81.33	82.3	67.62	78.2	76.2	80.3	65.15
	XMem + SAM B	85.59	84.06	87.28	72.43	83.4	80.4	86.5	74.21
	XMem + SAM MB	88.09	87.61	88.58	78.15	83.8	80.8	86.9	75.44
	XMem + SAM MP {C + P + S}	91.31	89.90	92.72	82.58	84.2	81.1	87.4	76.38
	XMem + SAM MBP {C + P + S}	91.38	89.99	92.77	82.67	84.6	81.2	88.0	76.19
	XMem + SAM MBPN {C + P + S}	91.38	89.99	92.77	82.67	87.2	84.1	90.3	79.7
Point	XMem + SAM MBPN {C}	89.77	88.73	90.82	80.52	86.9	83.8	90.0	78.36
	XMem + SAM MBPN {C + P}	91.27	90.2	92.33	83.13	87.2	84.1	90.2	79.67
	XMem + SAM MBPN {C + P + S}	91.38	89.99	92.77	82.67	87.2	84.1	90.3	79.7

Table 10
Ablation Study for XMem + HQ-SAM MBPN {C + P} on DAVIS datasets.

Model	DAVIS 2016 val				DAVIS 2017 val				
	$J&F$	J	F	AP	$J&F$	J	F	AP	
Prompt	XMem + HQ-SAM P {C + P}	86.11	86.4	85.83	74.81	72.9	69.3	76.5	00.00
	XMem + HQ-SAM BP {C + P}	86.59	86.31	86.88	74.58	75.4	71.8	78.9	61.22
	XMem + HQ-SAM BPN {C + P}	86.59	86.31	86.88	74.58	79.2	76.3	82.1	75.14
	XMem + HQ-SAM B	89.74	88.93	90.54	80.2	83.8	80.7	86.9	75.14
	XMem + HQ-SAM MB	90.97	90.59	91.36	83.66	84.5	81.4	87.6	76.67
	XMem + HQ-SAM MP {C + P}	91.68	90.68	92.68	83.99	83.6	80.4	86.8	75.55
	XMem + HQ-SAM MBP {C + P}	91.63	90.63	92.62	84.03	83.7	80.04	87.0	75.14
	XMem + HQ-SAM MBPN {C + P}	91.63	90.63	92.62	84.03	86.8	83.8	89.9	79.08
Point	XMem + HQ-SAM MBPN {C}	91.59	90.8	92.39	83.92	86.7	83.7	89.9	78.99
	XMem + HQ-SAM MBPN {C + P}	91.63	90.63	92.62	84.03	86.8	83.8	89.9	79.08
	XMem + HQ-SAM MBPN {C + P + S}	91.34	90.16	92.51	83.14	86.6	83.4	89.7	78.71

network models used are heavy and, although they show outstanding performance in terms of segmentation accuracy, for the moment they limit their use in real time in standard computers.

In this work we have identified different possible configurations of prompts to adjust the system, however, we have not applied a rigorous optimization methodology to identify the optimal configuration, allowing future work to explore these alternatives.

The proposed approach is based on the hypothesis that XMem is responsible for maintaining the temporal dependencies of the masks across its various memory states, while SAM ensures segmentation accuracy by mitigating temporal vanishing. However, brute force is applied to both systems, and prolonged object occlusion, coupled with appearance changes due to variations in lighting or context, is reliant solely on the information stored in XMem's memory. Consequently, significant degradation of these masks may result in false negatives that cannot be refined subsequently.

In addition, future work will involve the integration of new foundation models. Following the release of the 'Segment Anything Model,' numerous researchers have sought to optimize the model for specific problems. In this paper, we focus on the HQ-SAM model, but there are other variants, such as Mobile-SAM [58] and Fast-SAM [59]. Investigating how the VOS-E-SAM architecture performs with a version like Fast-SAM, which claims to be significantly faster in computing image embedding and segmentation, holds substantial promise for our research.

Finally, as a final work, the integration of a unified and lightweight architecture that exploits the spatial capabilities of SAM and the temporal capabilities of XMem.

7. Conclusions

This paper introduces an innovative architecture known as VOS-E-SAM, aimed at enhancing the results obtained from the leading video segmentation algorithms. This improvement is achieved by refining the masks for each frame using a foundational model, such as the SAM model. The SAM offers various ways of entering the prompt that

identifies the object for segmentation. In our experimentation, we have explored different prompt configurations to determine the best performance configuration for the VOS-E-SAM architecture. In addition, we have assessed the impact of coupling with the SAM model and its HQ-SAM version. These tests were performed using established domain-specific datasets for video segmentation. The results demonstrate an enhancement in most of the metrics for different video and object scenarios, particularly in Long Video datasets, on the XMem model, which serves as our baseline. The models were designed and tuned through an interactive process in which users receive new masks in each iteration, looking for the best input to correct any shortcomings in the output. In this case, we have used the model with a single input, primarily due to the challenges associated with defining a supervision framework, making it challenging to fully unlock the capabilities of such models while validating their results in a single prompting mode.

Most of state-of-the-art models troubles segmenting objects far from the beginning of the video is due to losing certain parts of the masks progressively like border definition or actual complete piece of the object due to occlusions, camera movements and perspective alterations. This behavior suggest that the trained model loses object and shape information as it advances through the frames. Knowing this, XMem is used in the architecture to track the object needed to be segmented, and the power of SAM is used to refine the masks in order to achieve better accuracy and contour definition. This can be seen in several figures presented in the paper.

The improvement on video metrics jaccard index (J) and contour accuracy (F) obtained on mean, decay and recall for LVOS and all but decay on LongDataset demonstrate that the proposed architecture is capable of pushing the performance boundary of SVOS systems, despite the already high baseline established by the base models. Furthermore, the proposed architecture is also likely to enhance the performance of any video segmentation models.

The ablation study shows that the addition of masks to the input configurations significantly improves segmentation performance on

long videos with a single-object, while simpler configurations, particularly with HQ-SAM, yield results comparable to SOTA. These results validate the robustness and adaptability of VOS-E-SAM and provide new opportunities to optimize input prompts and guide future developments.

It is important to note that this work has not focused on computational efficiency, and the performance in this regard has not been evaluated. The heavy computational demands of the neural network models currently limit real-time use on standard computers. For that reason the architecture proposed can have the potential to assist in annotation processes for video segmentation research easing the process of new dataset creation. Traditional annotation methods are labor-intensive and susceptible to human-induced errors. Future research could also explore other foundational models, such as Mobile-SAM or Fast-SAM, to enhance computational speed and efficiency.

In conclusion, the VOS-E-SAM architecture demonstrates its ability to enhance video segmentation systems, providing a foundation for future research to build upon by integrating more efficient and optimized models and configurations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Javier Pita: Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Juan P. Llerena:** Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Miguel A. Patricio:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Antonio Berlanga:** Validation, Supervision, Investigation. **Luis Usero:** Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

We have used public datasets.

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